

EXPLORING THE LIVED EXPERIENCES OF WORK-LIFE BALANCE AND JOB SATISFACTION AMONG ELDERLY HEALTHCARE WORKERS APPROACHING RETIREMENT

Irene B. Ambojnon, Montano Angelo A. Campos, Blessie Angelique C. De Castro, El Kiara S. Labatete, Khimberly C. Siasol

Psychology Department, World Citi Colleges – Quezon City, Quezon City, Philippines

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ABSTRACT

The study explores the lived experiences of work-life balance among elderly workers approaching retirement. This study employed a descriptive phenomenological approach in its research design. The aim of this study is to examine the relationship between work-life balance and job satisfaction among elderly healthcare workers through descriptive phenomenological approach. The respondents of this study will come from the elderly healthcare worker population within the vicinity of Quezon City, ranging in age from 55 to 65 years old. The study concludes that the elderly healthcare workers view work-life balance and job satisfaction as factors that positively impacts their overall well-being, productivity, and fulfillment. The study's findings put emphasis on the challenges elderly healthcare workers face, such as heavy workloads, rigid organizational policies, and insufficient support systems, which hinder their ability to maintain balance and satisfaction. It also highlights the importance of flexible work arrangements, retirement planning, and wellness programs in fostering a sustainable and meaningful career in healthcare.

Keywords: *Work – Life Balance, Job Satisfaction, Elderly Healthcare Worker*

INTRODUCTION

Healthcare professionals are trained and qualified to provide medical or health related services to patients. They are the ones who play a crucial role in maintaining the

health and well-being of an individual. Healthcare workers are known as doctors, nurses, laboratory technicians, therapists etc. Being a healthcare worker is not easy, balancing work from the hospital with responsibility at home is not easy. According to (Dousin et al. 2019), healthcare industry workers are often required to work in fixed schedules and shifts, which can lead to increased work-life conflict. The conflict is caused by an individual's difficulty in reconciling the demands of their career, family, and personal life. Work-life balance (WLB) is the amount of time spent between work and personal life. In addition, work-life balance is about creating and maintaining a supportive and healthy work environment, which will enable employees to balance between work and personal life (Nadesan, 2018). Balancing work and personal life has become an increasingly important topic in today's fast-paced and demanding professional world. Health care workers in particular face challenges in achieving and maintaining work life balance due to the nature of work.

Job satisfaction (JS) is defined as an individual's total fulfillment, joy, or happiness from work or employment. It is a subjective and complicated emotional and psychological condition caused by a person's view of their job and their experiences at work. Moreover, job satisfaction affects the intended retirement age and has yielded conflicting findings, that there might be moderating and mediating factors at play. Job satisfaction does, indeed, seem to impact a general retirement outlook, but this influence is more pronounced among workers with moderate to low household incomes. In contrast, for those with higher household incomes, other elements like the meaningfulness of their work, their social status, and the relationships formed through employment may offset or substitute for any decrease in job satisfaction (Davies et al., 2017). Working in late fifties or nearly is simply known as another decade of challenges and difficulties, especially for the elderly workers, whose bodies become weaker, but they also accumulate years of knowledge and skills from their work in the field. Work-life balance disparities is an unequal or uneven distribution of the time, energy, and attention that individuals can dedicate to their work and personal lives. It implies that some individuals or groups face greater challenges in achieving a balance between their work-related responsibilities and their personal or family lives, while others may find it easier to maintain this balance.

The aim of this study is to explore and gain a deeper understanding of the lived experiences of work-life balance and job satisfaction among elderly healthcare workers who are approaching retirement. By using a descriptive phenomenological approach, the study seeks to uncover themes on how these healthcare workers manage their work-life balance. Furthermore, it will investigate how these experiences influence their overall work-life balance and job satisfaction as they transition toward retirement. The findings will offer valuable information for shaping organizational strategies and guidelines to help this group within the healthcare industry.

Research Questions

This study explored the lived experiences of work-life balance and job satisfaction among elderly healthcare workers approaching retirement in Quezon City. Specifically, the study sought to answer the following question:

What are the potential implications of understanding the lived experiences of work-life balance and job satisfaction among elderly healthcare workers for organizational policies and practices aimed at supporting aging workforce transitions and improving overall well-being?

METHODOLOGY

The research design, sampling, data collection, and analysis techniques are all covered in this chapter. Their lived experiences are captured using a descriptive phenomenological approach. To guarantee reliable results, ethical issues and validity and reliability measures are also covered.

Research Locale

The study was carried out in public and private hospitals or clinics located in Quezon City, Philippines, with an emphasis on investigating the actual experiences of senior healthcare workers regarding work-life balance and job satisfaction.

Research Participants

Five elderly healthcare workers residing in Quezon City, who were purposefully chosen, served as the study's informants. In phenomenological research, a sample size of between five and twenty-five participants was typically considered adequate (Sarfo et al., 2021). Furthermore, the study noted that phenomenological research often employed small sample sizes. These participants had 10 to 15 years of experience in the healthcare industry, regardless of whether they maintained a regular or irregular work schedule. It was anticipated that their extensive experience and distinct viewpoints would provide significant insights to the study. Purposive sampling was used in their selection. According to (Denieffe 2020), purposive sampling is a qualitative research technique that selects a sample by considering important individual opinions with the aim of identifying cases that fit predetermined criteria. The target population consisted of senior healthcare professionals aged between 55 and 65 who worked in various healthcare facilities near Quezon City.

Data Gathering Procedures

The researchers selected five healthcare workers nearing retirement, aged 55 to 65 years old, for an in-depth interview. After selecting the participants, the researchers and respondents agreed on a schedule for the interview.

Before the in-depth interview began, the researchers explained the informed consent process and asked the respondents to sign an Informed Consent Form (ICF) before proceeding. By signing the ICF, participants acknowledged that they understood the purpose of the study and agreed to participate voluntarily.

After obtaining consent, the researchers conducted the in-depth interviews. The gathered data were then collected and analyzed using the Descriptive Phenomenological Approach. Throughout the interview, the researchers strictly adhered to the established in-depth interview protocol and meticulously documented all respondents' responses. Additionally, the researchers transcribed the interview recordings and interpreted themes from the data.

Research Instrument

An in-depth interview was conducted to investigate the lived experiences of work-life balance and job satisfaction among senior healthcare workers who were nearing retirement. In-depth interviews are a qualitative research method used to conduct detailed studies with a limited number of participants. Researchers examined respondents' opinions, experiences, emotions, and viewpoints regarding a specific topic or issue by using open-ended interview questions that provided rich qualitative data (Rutledge & Hogg, 2020). In-depth interviews had several benefits: they were flexible, could be readily adjusted to the participants' responses, allowed the interviewer to observe tone characteristics, and yielded comprehensive information.

Before the interview began, the researchers prepared four-item questions and validated by professional. In order to obtain informed consent, the researchers established rapport with the participants and explained the study's objectives, confidentiality protocols, and their rights to voluntary participation. Once everything was in order, the researchers began the interview by concentrating on the first section, which addressed the significance of work-life balance. This was followed by a second section discussing factors that influenced job satisfaction, and a third section discussing the implications for organizational policies and practices. Following the interview, the researchers informed the participants about the next phase of the research process and expressed gratitude for their insightful comments. The respondents also expressed their willingness to answer any additional questions or concerns and were assured that the information provided would be kept in the strictest confidence.

In addition, an Informed Consent Form (ICF) served as an instrument in the study to obtain permission from the chosen respondents before conducting the in-depth interview. The purpose of this form was to obtain consent from the respondents to conduct the interview, inform them of the confidentiality of their responses, and ensure that the data would be used solely for academic purposes.

Data Analysis

In this study, the researcher employed a descriptive phenomenological approach to analyze participants' experiences as described by them. This method involved several key steps to ensure a comprehensive understanding of the phenomenon under investigation. Initially, data were collected through in-depth, open-ended interviews, allowing participants to share detailed accounts of their experiences. These interviews were then transcribed verbatim to preserve the authenticity of the participants' narratives.

Following transcription, the researcher immersed themselves in the data by reading and rereading the transcripts multiple times to become intimately familiar with the content. Significant statements were identified, and meanings were formulated from these statements, which were then organized into clusters of themes. To ensure the accuracy and credibility of the findings, these themes were presented to experts for validation. Finally, the researcher compiled a comprehensive narrative report, discussing the implications of the findings and situating them within the context of existing literature.

Scope and Limitations

The scope of this study was to explore and understand the lived experiences of work-life balance and job satisfaction among elderly healthcare workers approaching retirement. The research focused on the unique perspectives of healthcare workers in their late careers, aged between 55 and 65 years. The study used a qualitative research approach along with in-depth interviews for data collection. The obtained data were analyzed using the Descriptive Phenomenological Approach (DPA) to describe the significance and essence of their experiences.

The research was conducted within the Quezon City area, focusing on elderly healthcare workers employed in medical fields. A sample of five purposively chosen participants was included to provide comprehensive insights into their job satisfaction and work-life balance as healthcare workers, as well as how these factors influenced their overall well-being as they neared retirement.

The limitations of the research, due to its qualitative nature, were that the data findings were obtained from only five respondents, which might restrict the applicability of the results to a larger population of elderly healthcare workers. The study was limited to the Quezon City area, and the experiences of healthcare workers regarding different organizational policies, cultural norms, or social situations were based on self-reported data via in-depth interviews. The findings may have been influenced by the participants' own biases, perceptions, and emotions. Additionally, the time available for conducting interviews and analyzing data might have impacted the depth and breadth of the study. Some participants may have felt uncomfortable discussing personal experiences related to work-life balance, job satisfaction, and retirement, which could have limited the richness of the collected data.

This study aimed to contribute valuable insights to enhance support systems for elderly healthcare workers and shape organizational strategies. It was relevant to various groups, including elderly healthcare workers, healthcare professionals, families of elderly workers, and future researchers interested in exploring similar topics.

RESULTS

This section presents the findings from comprehensive in-depth interviews exploring the lived experiences of work-life balance and job satisfaction among elderly

healthcare workers transitioning to retirement. The results are organized into the following categories: work-life balance, job satisfaction, the role of work-life balance in enhancing productivity and fulfillment, and organizational policies and support systems.

Major Themes	Sub-themes	Descriptive Summary
Work-Life Balance	Importance of Work-Life Balance for Individual's Well-Being	<p>Participants in the study emphasized the significant role of work-life balance (WLB) in safeguarding overall well-being. Most agreed that balancing work and personal life is essential to prevent feelings of overwhelm, stress, and eventual burnout. Some highlighted the importance of setting clear boundaries between work and personal time as an effective strategy for managing this balance.</p> <p>Additionally, participants mentioned that work-life balance helps in managing mental health problems. These insights align with existing research indicating that maintaining a healthy work-life balance is crucial for reducing stress, improving health, and enhancing productivity. Establishing clear boundaries between work and personal life can help prevent burnout and maintain overall well-being.</p>
	Work-Life Balance for Managing Priorities and Reducing Burnout	<p>Participants in the study emphasized work life balance for managing priorities and reducing stress. Most Participants answered that managing work-life balance helps to avoid stress, overwhelm and burn out. When at work, the participants focus on responsibilities that include managing patient schedules, records and coordinating with the specific doctors to ensure that everything runs smoothly during their shift.</p> <p>At home, participants make sure to leave work behind and focus on the family. By managing work life balance and priorities, participants can reduce</p>

		<p>burn out, overworking and taking work from home. Participants highlighted setting boundaries at work and at home as well as prioritizing tasks as helpful in reducing burn-out.</p>
	<p>Balancing Family and Professional Life</p>	<p>Participants in the study emphasized the importance of balancing family and personal life along with professional commitments. The majority of participants acknowledged that achieving this balance is not an easy task. However, making an effort to balance family and work responsibilities helps to reduce stress and prevent burnout and increase healthy relationships.</p> <p>Several participants highlighted that maintaining balance between family and professional life allows them to manage their time more effectively ensuring that neither family life nor professional duties are neglected. By giving equal time and attention to both family and work, setting priorities, individuals can minimize the conflict that often arises when one aspect of life is prioritized over the other. In addition, some participants mentioned that turning off work notifications help them to have some time with their family.</p>
		<p>Participants in the study emphasized the mental health benefits of maintaining a proper work-life balance (WLB) in healthcare. Some respondents noted that balancing work and personal life is very essential in preventing negative mental health outcomes such as stress, overwhelm and burnout. Some respondents shared how work-life balance helps to avoid the feelings of being "disconnected" from the people and activities that are important.</p>

	Mental Health Benefits of Work-Life Balance	<p>By emphasizing the importance of mental health through balanced living, participants in the study affirmed that achieving work-life balance isn't just about managing time but it is about sustaining mental wellness, preventing exhaustion, and fostering healthy relationships which are key to thrive both professionally and personally. Participants ensured that they have time for their hobbies to recharge and reflect on themselves.</p>
Job Satisfaction	Impact of a Productive Work-Life Balance	<p>Participants in the study emphasized the significant impact of job satisfaction on their work-life balance. Many expressed that their satisfaction stemmed from the joy of assisting patients, observing positive outcomes from their efforts, and genuinely enjoying their work. This sense of fulfillment contributed to a more harmonious balance between their professional and personal lives.</p> <p>These findings align with existing research indicating that job satisfaction is closely linked to work-life balance among healthcare workers. Studies have shown that a healthy work environment promotes job satisfaction, reduces burnout, and improves the quality of patient care. Additionally, achieving work-life balance has been associated with higher job satisfaction and better mental health. Participants also highlighted the importance of job satisfaction and having a balanced work and life.</p>
		<p>The participants in this study emphasized that having the sense of job satisfaction is a major key motivator, encouraging them to do</p>

	<p>Increased Job Satisfaction and Motivation</p>	<p>better in their respective jobs. They expressed that feeling fulfilled at work not only improves their work performance but also boosts their sense of achievement and morale in tackling challenges. Participants highlight that job satisfaction is related to work-life balance and work-life balance is a factor in having job satisfaction.</p>
<p>Work-Life Balance in Enhancing Productivity and Fulfillment</p>	<p>Work-Life Balance as a Key to Productivity</p>	<p>The participants consistently stated that work-life balance directly affects their productivity, taking time to rest and recharge outside of work allows them to return to their tasks with more focus, energy, and motivation. Participants also stated that who maintain balance can work smarter, not harder, ensuring that their efforts produce better results. Additionally, being well-rested and mentally refreshed allows them to approach work with a clear mind and a positive attitude. A well-maintained balance between work and life also fosters resilience, enabling individuals to manage stress more effectively and maintain high levels of performance even during challenging periods. Taking time to rest also shows positivity in enhancing productivity and fulfillment for the elderly healthcare workers.</p> <p>Participants stated that prioritizing work-life balance not only enhances individual productivity but also contributes to greater job satisfaction and fulfillment, creating a healthier and more engaged workforce. In addition, they also stated that being cared for at work helps them boost their productivity and fulfillment.</p>

	Preventing Burnout	<p>Work-life balance was recognized as an important factor in preventing burnout and maintaining mental health. Based on participants answer, they mentioned and explained that establishing boundaries between work and personal life reduces stress that allows them to remain resilient in the face of workplace challenges. In addition, participants said that without these boundaries, long work hours and constant pressure can result in mental exhaustion, decreased productivity, and even physical health issues.</p> <p>And so prioritizing balance, they are better equipped to handle their responsibilities without feeling overwhelmed. These boundaries help participants to recharge during personal time, ensuring that they return to work refreshed and capable of performing their tasks more effectively. In addition to, maintaining balance also promotes emotional well-being, reducing anxiety and enhancing overall job satisfaction.</p>
	Achieving Fulfillment in Personal Life	<p>Participants highlighted that achieving work-life balance enhances personal fulfillment by fostering stronger relationships, providing time for personal growth, and ensuring emotional well-being. Additionally, they described how compartmentalizing work and home life allows them to fully engage with their families and enjoy meaningful personal experiences. They shared that leaving work stress at the workplace enables them to be present with their loved ones, which contributes to better relationships and a greater sense of satisfaction in life.</p> <p>Furthermore, the work life balance also allows participants to feel more in</p>

		control of their lives, reducing the risk of feeling overwhelmed or disconnected. Dedicating time to their personal lives, participants were able to recharge, reconnect with themselves, and gain a sense of fulfillment that was directly linked to their overall well-being. The sense of control and emotional satisfaction ultimately contributed to a more positive and productive approach to work, creating a balance that benefited both personal and professional spheres.
Organizational Policies and Support Systems	Flexible Working Arrangements	Most of the participants' responses correspond to how flexible working schedules result in the reduction of their stress levels, as well as having a better balance between their life at work, life at home and doing their personal wants, as a form of relaxation for themselves. Benefits that they will get once the organizational policies and support systems are implemented, give them the feeling that their years of serving others are being paid – off in ways that they did not expect, as a way of thanking them for how much effort they give into making sure that the public's well-being is being taken care of.
	Individual Ways of Coping to Maintain Mental Health	Most of the participants developed their own ways to maintain their mental health adapting to the demands of their work schedules. Most responses revealed that relying on proposed organizational policies for better work-life balance would only lead to disappointment so they took initiative to maintain their work-life balance ensuring to balance effectively by having time for themselves, family and at work allowing them to stay motivated and avoid burnout.

	<p>Hopes Wishes</p> <p>and</p>	<p>Participants highlighted that implementation of organizational policies and support systems gives them joy and relief and it helps them to maintain a balance between work and life. However, some mentioned that organizational support is lacking in their workplace leaving elderly workers with little guidance in preparing for retirement whether financially, emotionally or practically. Programs like counseling sessions could help them boost their confidence and readiness on and before retirement.</p> <p>In addition, participants also stated wellness programs could help them sustain their strength and motivation. Knowing that their well-being is being prioritized, the sense of appreciation could inspire them to extend their years of service.</p>
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DISCUSSION

This part of the paper presents the data and analysis of the findings obtained from the responses to the questionnaire. This presents the themes formulated from work-life balance, job satisfaction and organizational policies and support system.

Balancing Work and Personal Demands

Balancing work and life demands is essential for maintaining overall well-being and productivity, particularly in high-stress industries like healthcare. The study participants emphasized that achieving work-life balance (WLB) helps prevent stress, burnout, and emotional exhaustion. Research supports this, indicating that organizational support plays a key role in helping employees manage work and personal responsibilities effectively (Ahmad et al, 2021). Establishing clear boundaries between work and home life allows individuals to prioritize self-care, engage in meaningful relationships, and maintain mental well-being, ultimately fostering a healthier and more motivated workforce.

Moreover, WLB contributes significantly to managing priorities and reducing burnout. Participants shared that when they are at work, they focus entirely on their responsibilities, such as managing patient schedules and coordinating with doctors, but once at home, they disconnect from work-related stress (Misra & Kar, 2019). This

approach aligns with research findings that employees who maintain a proper work-life balance are more productive and experience lower burnout rates. Additionally, work-life balance improves emotional resilience and cognitive focus, allowing employees to perform efficiently while reducing the risks associated with prolonged work-related stress.

Another crucial aspect of work-life balance is its impact on mental health. Participants emphasized that a well-maintained balance helps prevent feelings of disconnection from loved ones and personal interests, which are critical for emotional stability (Misra & Kar, 2019). Research indicates that employees with a strong work-life balance report higher job satisfaction and better psychological well-being. This balance enables them to sustain meaningful relationships, avoid excessive stress, and perform effectively in both personal and professional settings.

Despite its importance, achieving work-life balance remains a challenge due to excessive workloads and rigid workplace policies. Some participants noted that inflexible schedules hinder their ability to manage personal responsibilities effectively (Irfan et al., 2023). Studies show that organizations that prioritize flexibility, such as allowing remote work or flexible schedules, experience lower employee turnover and higher job satisfaction. Implementing policies that support employees in maintaining a balanced lifestyle can lead to a healthier and more engaged workforce, reducing burnout and enhancing overall productivity.

The findings show that work-life balance is not just about time management but about sustaining well-being, preventing exhaustion, and fostering professional fulfillment. Participants shared that achieving balance allows them to serve their families wholeheartedly while excelling in their careers. Research reinforces that a well-balanced lifestyle leads to higher job performance, increased motivation, and greater personal fulfillment. Employers who invest in work-life balance initiatives can create a more sustainable and productive work environment, benefiting both individuals and organizations alike (Ahmad et al., 2022; Misra & Kar, 2019; Irfan et al., 2023).

Importance of Job satisfaction and Work-life Balance in Achieving Fulfillment

Job satisfaction has a significant influence on the entire well-being of an individual. It directly influences their sense of fulfillment, motivation, work-life balance, and contentment. The participants in the study explained that their sense of satisfaction came from helping others, experiencing the beneficial effects of their efforts, and feeling appreciated and respected for all their contributions. Also, the participants highlighted the importance of having a balance in terms of personal life and professional life; it allows the participants to stay engaged and feel motivated and psychologically equipped to handle the job expectations.

The work-life balance was often cited by the participants as a key component of their job satisfaction. They stated that after they effectively manage professional and personal commitments, they are more satisfied overall and struggle less with burnout and stress. This aligns with the results of Dousin et al. (2019), who indicated that flexible work

schedules contribute to a healthier work environment and lower professional and personal conflicts, resulting in a more good and positive work-life environment. The respondents stated higher job satisfaction is when they feel appreciated in their jobs and able to see the beneficial influence of their work. This highlights the significance of a workplace environment that prioritizes the overall well-being of the employees.

Additionally, job satisfaction was found to be a significant motivator that promotes the employees to perform better, stay motivated, and thrive in their work responsibilities. According to the participants, when they feel satisfied, they approach their work with enthusiasm and become more resilient when facing difficulties. It gives the employees a sense of stability, gratitude, and motivation. Organizational support has a big influence on job satisfaction (Naig & Borbon, 2021). Furthermore, burnout, which reduces motivation and job performance, is caused by a poor work-life balance. These findings demonstrate how crucial it is to create a supportive and safe work environment and work-life balance in order to maintain overall job satisfaction (Wong et al., 2021).

The findings show that work-life balance and job satisfaction are closely connected, with effective balance leading to increased motivation, engagement, and productivity. Organizations that foster a positive and healthy environment throughout the flexible and creative work arrangements, acknowledgement, and optimistic culture can decrease burnout and improve the overall job performance of healthcare workers.

The Importance of Work-Life Balance in Enhancing Productivity, Well-Being and Personal Fulfillment

The study's participants stated that with the help of a proper work-life balance, it results in the significant increase in productivity at work, which leads to improvement in one's own well-being, not just in a physical sense, but also emotionally, socially and mentally. Having a proper balance of work-life and life at home means that by the time they return home from work, they have already left behind the stress from work and turn their attention to their responsibilities at home. A proper work-life balance prevents burnout, because they know how to manage their time, and prioritize what needs to be done first. In a study conducted, wherein work-life balance can affect issues such as job turnovers, stress, organizational commitment, absenteeism, job satisfaction and productivity (Gumpal & Cardenas, 2021). This previous study's results align with the current study's results, since they point out how work-life balance can lead to lesser conflicts, and increases productivity. Moreover, the current study puts emphasis on the importance of having a moment to relax with your loved ones at home, since it can lessen stress levels brought about by work.

There is also the statement that work-life balance helps in establishing boundaries between work-life and personal life, so as to avoid conflicts between responsibilities at home and at work. Establishing these boundaries helps in maintaining the stability of one's own well-being, since it prevents chronic stress which may lead to mental fatigue and exhaustion, which can lead to a wide variety of illnesses, an example of which is high blood pressure. Through the use of these boundaries, employees know that what is only

at work, stays at work, and what is at home stays at home. There is also the element of maintaining focus, because with work-life balance, a person, especially an employee, knows what they need to prioritize, and what they should focus on. According to a study conducted by Gaur et al. (2021), results show that when people, employees especially, experience occupational stress, or are stressed out with their jobs and are unable to cope with it, it badly affects their work-life balance, which will then lead to dissatisfaction towards their job. Based on this study, variables that may lead to occupational stress depend on an individual employee's management of their time at work and at home, as well as their overall satisfaction and fulfillment with their job. To align this with the current study, it establishes the importance of having boundaries between work and personal life, since this allows an employee to have control over their own time, and not feel pressured to comply with tasks even at home.

However, participants still face significant challenges in achieving that delicate balance of work-life and home life, which causes them to feel dissatisfied towards their job. These factors inside the workplace can influence how long they will work inside the said organization, whether they will stay loyal to their organization despite the toxicity of the workplace, or submit a letter of resignation to go work in another healthcare facility, in hopes of having a much healthier, non-toxic, and productive workplace. However, finding such an ideal workplace that can accommodate their age group would be a rare sight, since even elderly healthcare workers are forced to work in extended periods of time, as mentioned by some respondents. In alignment with a previous study, conducted by Wong et al. (2021), it states that elderly workers face the dilemma of experiencing health issues due to the imbalance between work-life and personal life. This is due to the lack of rest between work days, which results in burnout. This previous study aligns with the current study, as it shows that workplace toxicity can have significant negative effects on an employee's overall well-being. To add to this, it shows the reality that even industries that circle around the care of a person's physical well-being, values output rather than their own employee's health.

Lastly, the participants stated that work-life balance helps them have a general sense of fulfillment and satisfaction towards their job. This is due to having the time to relax for themselves, it helps in easing the pent-up stress that accumulated throughout an entire day of working. This then fosters better relationships with co-workers, which enhances an employee's emotional and social well-being. Going home from work while carrying stress and left-over papers or any job-related tasks back at home proves to be detrimental to the overall well-being of an employee, as it can be the leading cause of many kinds of diseases due to chronic stress that developed in the workplace. In a study conducted by Licudan-Creto & Naparota (2022), the study states that employees have a good knowledge of job satisfaction and workplace quality of life, along with high emotional control over their life satisfaction and quality of work life. This then results in the employees being able to accomplish many work-related tasks without feeling stressed out or exhausted. In alignment with the current study's results and findings, being satisfied or feeling fulfilled with one's job is a great source of motivation to go to work for another day. Moreover, the study also puts emphasis on how job satisfaction influences how an employee performs in their job, with high job satisfaction showing significant improvement

in job performance, while low job satisfaction results in declining job performance, which may result in resignations or job turnovers when it worsens over time.

The finding shows that work-life balance positively impacts productivity and well-being of the employees, which in turn leads to feeling of fulfillment in the job, or job satisfaction. Work-life balance makes an employee more productive through sufficient amount of rest and relaxation, and by establishing boundaries between work-life and home life. This is because it makes an employee feel more energized or recharged to go to work for another day, as well as feel more in control over their own time, and have the right to leave work and stress behind the office to spend time with their loved ones. Due to these benefits of work-life balance towards their lives at work and at home, employees have a greater sense of satisfaction towards their job, which then strengthens organizational loyalty and commitment. Challenges, however, may still arise, such as workplace toxicity, which can negatively impact work-life balance and job satisfaction. This just goes to show that the reality of work-life is very stressful in itself, if not managed properly.

Effects of Organizational Policies and Support Systems to Maintain a Healthy Work Life Balance

Organizational policies and support systems for elderly healthcare workers positively impacts their work-life balance and job satisfaction. Flexible working arrangements help to manage work and family commitments, reducing stress, and helps in mental health problems caused by burnout. According to Previtali et al. (2022), stated that the health of older workers is a key factor in the extension of working lives among occupational health professionals. Health is not limited to physical or mental health issues, but also encompasses the ability to manage health requirements at work and maintain a healthy, sustainable, and responsible balance between various areas, including health and work. As the workforce ages and working lives are extended, it is becoming a strategic management objective for companies to support and retain older workers. This balance between work and health is particularly important for older workers, as work-health balance is partially related to work ability but not to job performance as assessed by supervisors. . Therefore, it is not only the ability to work that matters, but also the organization's health climate and the supervisor's support. In addition, organizational policies and support systems also help in the job satisfaction of elderly healthcare workers. Healthcare workers feel motivated to work when they know that their organization is at their back supporting them as they transition, leading to a better performance.

In another study by Dousin et al. (2019), it states that in a highly competitive work environment, such as the healthcare industry, the implementation of flexible working arrangements and supportive supervision is essential in order to attract, retain and motivate employees. In this study, work-life conflicts are a result of healthcare workers working in fixed schedules and shifts, and are reduced through employer-driven flexible work schedules and supportive supervision. Conflicts, in this study, are also a result of an individual's difficulty with managing demands from both at home and at work. This

previous study aligns with the current study in terms of the importance being put in the implementation of flexible working arrangements, since by having a flexible working schedule, employees can balance their time at work and at home, leading to less stress due to conflicts at work and responsibilities with the family, therefore improving their work-life balance. Moreover, by having a flexible working schedule, satisfaction of employees towards their job increases.

In the last related study by Nugroho et al. (2022), it states that job satisfaction among employees is highly valuable to an organization because it enhances loyalty towards the organization and employee productivity. According to this study, happy employees tend to be more productive and have a better job performance than those that are dissatisfied with their job. Employee retention is influenced by job satisfaction, and a critical factor affecting job satisfaction is work-life balance. This previous study aligns with the current study, since this previous study is similar in how the current study views the connection between work-life balance and job satisfaction, and how this affects the experiences of elderly healthcare workers throughout their career. Throughout their career, elderly healthcare workers' experience in balancing their lives at work and at home can be delicate and prone to be disrupted.

The findings show that organizational policies and support systems are crucial for elderly healthcare workers. Elderly workers emphasize that implementation of organizational policies and support systems like flexible work schedules, retirement planning programs and wellness initiatives helps them physically, mentally, emotionally and financially stable as they transition to retirement. Having a flexible working schedule, participating in wellness initiatives, training, and being supervised in a supportive way by supervisors result in loyalty towards the organization, as well as retaining and attracting prospective employees. This will then lead to lesser conflicts in the workplace, since frequent conflicts between employees are a result of stress in the job as well as frustration towards the management. For elderly healthcare workers, experiencing such benefits will give them the motivation to show a better job performance until the day that they will retire.

Conclusions

This research studied the lived experiences of work-life balance and job satisfaction among older healthcare professionals approaching retirement, and how these influence their overall well-being, productivity, and satisfaction. Using a phenomenological method, the research identified that work-life balance is important in reducing stress, avoiding burnout, and ensuring mental health, while job satisfaction is an important driver, creating a sense of purpose and professional satisfaction.

The results highlighted elderly healthcare workers' challenges, including too much workloads, inflexible organizational policies, and insufficient systems of support that undermine their maintenance of balance and satisfaction. The research highlighted the importance of developing personalized organizational policies, including flexibility in working times and wellness schemes, to serve the needs of older workers in order to

know a sustainable and satisfactory transition towards retirement. By gaining work-life balance and job satisfaction, older healthcare workers are not only able to work at their best performance but also keeping healthier personal and professional relationships and development. Closing systemic gaps and developing supportive environments will be an advantage to both workers and the healthcare industry by enhancing employees' well-being, turnover reduction, and keeping experienced staff.

Future work on resolving issues like lack of support systems for senior personnel and organizational policies and their impact on their well-being is made possible by this research. This work can be expanded by the researchers using mixed methodologies, ongoing studies, or larger samples in an effort to increase flexibility and get a deeper understanding of issues pertaining to the elderly workers. By connecting knowledge gaps at theoretical and practical levels, the work contributes in influencing policy, boosting workforce retention, and ensuring that health care systems continue to be tough while respecting the efforts of aging health care personnel.

It contributes to the greater viewpoint of aging workforce patterns through an examination into the work-life balance and job satisfaction experiences of older health care workers as they proceed to retirement. As it highlights the need of work-life balance in reducing stress, preventing burnout, and promoting mental wellness, it also highlights the unique challenges faced by this demographic.

The findings provide useful suggestions for enhancing employee flexibility and well-being while highlighting the importance of flexible work schedules, retirement savings, and health initiatives. By connecting work-life balance, job fulfillment, and job satisfaction, the research offers a way to creating sustainable and meaningful employment, especially in healthcare. It also gives authority to families to support elderly workers more and trains younger health care professionals with experiences to guide similar situations in the future.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following major recommendations are made to promote the job satisfaction and work-life balance of older healthcare workers on the brink of retirement:

Introduction of Tailored Organizational Policies. Hospitals should conduct policies that mainly address elderly workers, including phased retirement arrangements, wellness programs, mental health care and also such actions can relieve pressure and burnout.

Addressing Systemic Gaps. Companies have to review and revamp job structures within workplaces that cause dissatisfaction and imbalance, such as high workloads and strict policies and also adding resources, training, and mentorship opportunities for elderly workers can help fill these gaps.

Building Supportive Environments. It is essential to create a welcoming and age-friendly work place. Employers must build social support network, promote interpersonal working, and give leadership roles. Also, addressing weak support systems for elderly workers and determining the effects of organizational policies on their well-being can make a more supportive and sustainable work environment.

Implementing Flexible Work Arrangements. To be able to meet the needs of elderly healthcare workers, companies may offer flexible schedules, work from home where possible, and shorter-hour shifts. With these changes, it can improve job satisfaction without reducing productivity.

Through applying these recommendations, healthcare institutions can improve the health of elderly healthcare professionals, allowing them to continue and proceed into retirement in a convenient and fulfilling way. These strategies can also benefit the healthcare industry by reducing turnover, keeping qualified workers, and improving employment sustainability.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The protection of human rights was ensured during data collection for this research. Ethical considerations in this study included the following:

Informed Consent and Voluntary Participation

Participants were fully informed about the purpose of the study and were provided with comprehensive information. Additionally, they had the right to withdraw without facing any negative consequences. Consent was given freely and voluntarily, and participants were required to understand the study.

Confidentiality

The data and information gathered were kept anonymous unless the participants gave full consent.

Data Security

The data collected were secured against unauthorized access. The researchers ensured that the participants' data were safe and protected.

Validity Process

The researchers ensured that the interview questionnaires were validated by a designated validator to confirm the credibility of the questions. By using different data sources, such as interviews, they guaranteed the validity of the process through a thorough understanding of the respondents' answers. The researchers and respondents

shared the findings for transparency and to ensure accuracy and alignment with the participants' experiences.

The researchers also followed a strict interview protocol. They built rapport with the respondents, ensured that they understood the purpose of the interview and the informed consent—including their right to withdraw or participate—and assured them of confidentiality. The interview protocol consisted of three parts: Introduction, where researchers built rapport, explained the purpose of the interview and the study, confirmed that the participants understood the informed consent and their right to voluntarily participate or withdraw, and assured them of confidentiality; Interview Section where questions were asked, and follow-up questions were posed based on the respondents' answers; and Conclusion where researchers thanked the participants for their valuable insights and time, updated them on the next phase of the research process, reiterated confidentiality, and expressed their willingness to address any further questions or concerns.

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